

Evaluation Of Phytochemicals, Antioxidant Potential, And Antibacterial Properties of Plant: *Pennisetum Setaceum* (Forssk.) Chiov

Kinjal Damor¹, Riya Kadia², Nainesh Modi*³, Milan Dabhi⁴, Dweipayan Goswami⁵

¹MSc student, Department of Botany, Bioinformatics, Climate Change Impacts Management, Gujarat University, Ahmedabad.

²Research Scholar, Department of Botany, Bioinformatics, Climate Change Impacts Management, Gujarat University, Ahmedabad.

³Professor, Department of Botany, Bioinformatics, Climate Change Impacts Management, Gujarat University, Ahmedabad.

⁴Research Scholar, Department of Microbiology and Biotechnology, USSC, Gujarat University, Ahmedabad.

⁵Assistant Professor, Department of Microbiology and Biotechnology, USSC, Gujarat University, Ahmedabad

ABSTRACT

Pennisetum setaceum (Forssk.) Chiov. is an attractive grass plant that produces purple leaves. This plant is commonly called purple fountain grass. This plant belongs from the Poaceae family. *Pennisetum setaceum* (Forssk.) Chiov. is native to Africa. This research focused on the phytochemicals screening, antioxidant and antimicrobial activity of the plant *Pennisetum setaceum* (Forssk.) Chiov. Different plant parts like leaves and stem. Plant extract was prepared in the three different solvents like methanol, D.W., and hexane by cold extraction method. The qualitative analysis of plant parts shows that the secondary metabolites like alkaloids, phenols, tannins, phytosterols, and amino acids are present. The various quantitative methods like TPC, TTC, and TFC are used for total content determination. Methanolic extraction has the highest total content. In leaves methanolic extraction shows the highest value of TPC is 6.301 ± 0.00 GAE/G and also the highest value of TTC with value of 3.358 ± 0.071 TAE/g. Stem hexane extraction shows the highest value for TFC is 7.056 ± 0.033 QE/g. DPPH and PMA assays were used for the determination of antioxidant activity in different solvents of plant extracts, which determine the reducing agent that is present in the different parts of the plant. In the DPPH assay, the highest IC₅₀ value was present in the hexane extract of leaves with the value of 20.728. And in the PMA method, the highest total antioxidant capacity is shown in the D.W. extracts of the leaves with the value of 1.001 mg AAE/g. Antibacterial activity was checked against gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. *E. coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria were used for antibacterial activity checked in different plant extracts. The highest zone of inhibition is shown in the acetone extract of the stem with a 20 mm zone of inhibition.

Keywords: *Pennisetum setaceum* (Forssk.) Chiov., TPC, TTC, TFC, DPPH, PMA, antibacterial activity

INTRODUCTION

Pennisetum setaceum (Forssk.) Chiov., commonly referred to as purple fountain grass, is a type of purple-pigmented ornamental grass from the Poaceae family. *Pennisetum setaceum* (Forssk.) Chiov., which originated in Africa, is one of the most commonly used ornamental grasses worldwide. It has several landscaping applications, including border, erosion control, rock garden, and urban garden. It requires a

warm temperature to produce vibrant leaf color. Purple fountain grass was selected because it is evergreen, grows in hot regions, and is drought tolerant (Gonzalez-Rodriguez et al., 2010). It belongs to the C₄ grasses, which have a unique photosynthetic pathway. The shrub blooms widely throughout the summer and winter. The plant has wonderful qualities, including spikes of purple flowers that gracefully shoot from its numerous long colorful leaves (Williams & Black et al., 1996)

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Fig:1: Pennisetum setaceum (Forssk.) Chiov.

Phytochemicals are naturally occurring and physiologically active chemical compounds found in plants that beneficial for human health as nutrients and medicinal components (Hasler et al., 1999). They protect plants from disease and harm while also improving their color, aroma, and flavor. Phytochemicals are plant substances that protect the environment from pollutants, stress, dehydration, UV exposure, and infections (Gibson et al., 1998). Fruits, vegetables, legumes, whole grains, nuts, seeds, fungi, herbs, and spices contain a variety of phytochemicals (Mathai & K. 2000). Phytochemicals are plant-based substances with distinct pharmacological and physiological characteristics that are utilized in ethnomedicine to treat a variety of ailments. Antioxidant, antibacterial, antifungal, anti-inflammatory, anti-allergic, cancer, and heart diseases are just a few of the many vital roles they play in human health (Prakash et al., 2011). Antioxidants inhibit oxidation even at low concentration therefore, they serve a range of physiological functions in the body. Antioxidants serve as free radical scavengers, transforming reactive radicals into less active, less dangerous, and more powerful compounds. Antioxidants can neutralize free radicals by absorbing or providing electrons, which removes their unpaired position (Lü et al., 2010). Antioxidants are chemical compounds that prevent the oxidation of numerous substances with oxygen, including basic molecules, using polymers and complex (Bagchi et al., 1998). Antimicrobial activity describes a substance's ability to kill or decrease microorganisms such as bacteria, viruses, fungi, and parasites. Medicinal plants have an important function in preventing infections and

diseases caused by bacteria. Various plant parts, such as leaves, stems, and roots, were used for treatment, which was caused by bacteria, viruses, and fungus (Huang et al., 2019).

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

2.1 Plant sample collection:

Healthy and mature plant parts leaves and stem of *Pennisetum setaceum* (Forssk.) Chiov. was collected from campus area of Gujarat University on 9th January, 2025.

2.2 Prepration of plant extract:

Plant parts were sun-dried and crushed into powder form. Cold extraction method was used to form plant extracts. For this, took 10 g of plant powder in 100 ml of methanol, D.W., and hexane. Then put them in a rotary shaker for 24 hours. After 24 hours, the solutions were filtered with Whatman filter paper number 1. After filtering, the solutions are poured into petri plates and air-dried. To make the stock solution, 30 mg of dried plant extract was dissolved in 30 ml of methanol, D.W., and hexane. The stock solutions can later be used to perform various activities.

2.3 The qualitative analysis:

Secondary metabolites, including alkaloids, carbohydrataes, glycosides, saponin, phytosterols, phenols, tannins, flavonoids, protiens, and amino acids are studied using standerd techniques (Harbone, J. B. 1984).

Table 1: Qualitative analysis of phytochemical constituents (Shaikh and patil, 2020)

Phytochemicals components	Name of test	Procedure	Result
Alkaloids	Dragendroff's reagent	Few mL filtrate + 1-2 mL Dragendroff's reagent	A reddish-brown precipitate
	Myer's test	Few mL of filtrate + 1-2 drops Myers's reagent	Yellow precipitate
Phenols	Iodine test	1 mL extract + few drops of dil. Iodine sol.	A transient red colour
	Lead acetate test	Plant extract is dissolved in 5 mL distilled water + 3 mL of 10 % lead acetate sol.	A white precipitate
Flavonoids	Conc. H ₂ SO ₄ test	Plant extract + Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	An orange colour
	Lead acetate test	1 mL plant extract + few drops of 10 % lead acetate solution	A yellow precipitate
Tannins	Braymer's test	1 mL filtrate + 3 mL distilled water + 3 drops 10% ferric chloride solution	Blue-green colour
	10% NaOH test	0.4 mL plant extract + 4 mL NaOH + shaken well	Formation of emulsion
Amino acid	Ninhydrin test	2 mL filtrate + 2 drops of Ninhydrin solution	A purple coloured sol
	Millon's test	2 mL filtrate + few drops of Millon's reagent	A white precipitate
Phytosterol	Salkowski test	Filtrate + few drops of conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Red colour
	Hesse's response test	5 mL aq. Extract + 2 mL chloroform + 2 mL conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Pink ring

2.4 Qualitative analysis:

Several quantitative methods are used to quantify the estimation of secondary metabolites. Secondary metabolites help in adaptation and defence against several stress-related diseases.

2.4.1 Total phenol content (TPC):

The Folin-Ciocalteu method has used for total phenolic content determination. Gallic acid is used as standard. Various concentrations of plant extract are taken like (0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0 mg/ml). Then add 0.5 ml of the folin-Ciocalteu reagent then add 2 ml of 20% Na₂CO₃ to the test tube. Total concentration of test tube will be 3 ml. The test tubes were boiled for one minute in water bath. After the test tubes were cooled down at room temperature, the absorbance was measured at 650 nm (Somnawathi et al., 2015). The total phenolic content of extracts was calculated using the gallic acid equivalent for each gram of dry weight (mg GAE/g). The quantity of phenolic content in the plant sample was calculated by using the formula below:

$$\text{Total phenolic content: } \frac{\text{GAE} \times \text{V}}{\text{m}}$$

GAE: Gallic acid equivalent (mg/ml)

V: Volume of plant extract

2.4.2 Total Tannin content (TTC):

For determination of total tannin concentration, Folin-Ciocalteu method was used with slide modifications. For TTC, tannic acid is used as a standard. Took different range of plant extract concentration like 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1 mg/ml. Then add 7.5 ml of distilled water. Then add 0.5 ml folin phenol reagent to the mixture. Add 1 ml of 35% Na₂CO₃ and diluted with 10 ml of distilled water. The mixture was thoroughly mixed and kept at room temperature for 30 minutes. Take absorbance at 725 nm. (Lahare et al., 2021). Tannin content was calculated in mg of TAE/g of extracts. A calibration curve is created with tannic acid as the standard. To determine the tannic concentration of a plant sample, use the following formula:

$$\text{Total Tannin content: } \frac{\text{TAE} \times \text{V}}{\text{m}}$$

TAE: Tannic acid equivalent (mg/ml)

V: Volume of plant extract

2.4.3 Total flavonoids content (TFC):

The colorimetric test was used to determine the total flavonoid content. Quercetin is used as standard. Different concentrations of plant extract are taken like (0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0 mg/ml). Take 100 μ l of extract with 4 ml of distilled water. Then, 0.3 ml of 5% sodium nitrite was added. After 5 minutes, 0.3 ml of 10% aluminium chloride was added. Then add 2 ml of 1 M sodium hydroxide for 6 minutes. The mixture was diluted with 3.3 ml of distilled water and well mixed. The absorbance was measured at 510 nm (Zhishen et al., 1999). Using Quercetin as the standard, a calibration curve is created. To determine the flavonoid content of a plant sample, use the following formula:

$$\text{Total Flavonoids content: } \frac{QE \times V}{m}$$

QE: Quercetin equivalent (mg/ml)

V: Volume of plant extract

2.5 Antioxidant activity:

Antioxidants are chemical or natural molecules that can prevent cell damage. Antioxidants are stable compounds that transfer electrons to neutralize free radicals, reducing their harmful effects. Antioxidants have several functions, including hydrogen donation, radical scavenging, peroxide decomposition, singlet oxygen quenching, synergy, enzyme inhibition, and metal chelation. The present study examined the antioxidant activity of Pennisetum setaceum (Forssk.) Chiov. plants using several antioxidant methods (Gameti et al., 2023).

2.5.1 DPPH ASSAY:

1 ml of methanol and 1 mg of leaf extract. The standard and plant extract series were prepared in triplicate, with 1 ml of extract in each test tube and concentration ranging from 20 to 100 mg/ml. The standard is ascorbic acid. DPPH is light sensitive, so a fresh solution was prepared by dissolving 4 mg powdered DPPH in 100 ml of methanol and storing it in a dark area. After making series of extracts at various concentrations, 3 ml of DPPH solution was added and incubated for 20 to 30 minutes in dark. After some incubation, the purple solution created by

the addition of DPPH will turn pale yellow. The absorbance was measured at 517 nm (Pattani et al., 2023). The radical scavenging activity was calculated using the following equation:

$$\% \text{inhibition} = \frac{\text{Control} - \text{Sample}}{\text{Control}} \times 100$$

2.5.2 PMA ASSAY:

The method given by Prieto et al., (1999) was used with some modification. In this experiment, 0.2 ml of plant extract (1mg/ml stock) and standard ascorbic acid (0.2-1 ml) were mixed with Phosphomolybdate reagent. The reaction mixture was then incubated in a water bath for 90 minutes. After cooling to room temperature, the absorbance was measured at 695 nm. The antioxidant ability was reported as mg of ascorbic acid equivalents AAE/g of extract (Mankad et al., 2021).

$$\text{Antioxidant capacity: } \frac{AAE \times V}{m}$$

AAE: Ascorbic acid equivalents (mg/ml)

V: Volume of plant extract

2.6: Antibacterial activity:

Antimicrobial susceptibility has been examined using the agar well-diffusion technique. Escherichia coli and Staphylococcus aureus have been used to test the extract of Pennisetum setaceum (Forssk.) Chiov. for its capacity to inhibit the growth of the infection. To create colonies for sensitivity testing, each bacterial strain was cultivated into nutrient agar plates and incubated for 18 to 24 hours at 37°C. After an overnight incubation period, colonies were selected using a sterile disposable inoculating loop and then transferred to a glass tube containing sterile. Before the plates were streaked with bacteria, wells 5 mm in diameter were punched into the medium using sterile bores. All of the plates were filled with the bacterial sample. A sterile cotton swab was put into the solution. It was moved and gently pushed against the fluid level to remove any extra inoculum. After the bacterial inoculation of the plate, 50 μ l aliquots of each sample extract after the bacterial inoculation of the plates. To select the bacteria, three plates were used for each extract, and the same extract was poured in each plate. The plates are put in an incubator that is regulated at 37°C. After a 24-hor incubation period,

each plate was examined for an inhibited zone. Using a measuring instrument, the inhibited zones were measured in mm.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Qualitative analysis:

Table 1: Phytochemical screening or qualitative analysis

Secondary metabolites	Test	Solvent and plant parts					
		Methanol		Hexane		D.W.	
		Leaf	Stem	Leaf	Stem	Leaf	Stem
Alkaloids	Dragendroff's test	+	-	+	-	-	-
	Mayer's test	+	+	+	-	-	-
Phenols	Iodine test	+	+	-	-	-	-
	Lead acetate test	+	-	-	+	+	-
Flavonoids	Conc.H ₂ SO ₄ test	+	+	+	-	-	-
	Lead acetate test	+	+	-	-	-	-
Tannins	Braymer's test	+	+	-	-	+	-
	10% NAOH test	+	-	-	+	-	-
Amino acids	Ninhydrin test	+	-	-	-	-	-
	Millon's test	+	+	+	+	-	-
Phytosterol	Salkowski test	+	+	+	-	-	-
	Hesse's response test	+	-	-	+	-	-

('+' Presence of phytochemicals, '-' Absence of phytochemicals)

The maximum value of phenol is obtained in methanol extract of leaves with value of 6.301 ± 0.00 GAE/g while the lowest value of phenol is obtained in D.W. extract is 0.253 ± 0.005 TAE/g in plant leaves.

3.2 Quantitative analysis:

3.2.1 Total phenol content:

Table 2: Total phenolic content of plant sample

Plant parts	Concentration ml	Total phenolic content of extract		
		Methanol	D.W.	Hexane
leaves	1 ml	6.301 ± 0.00	0.253 ± 0.005	6.301 ± 0.00
Stem	1 ml	4.724 ± 0.078	-0.111 ± 0.014	6.113 ± 0.010

3.2.2 Total tannin content:

The maximum concentration of total tannin content is obtained in methanol extract are 3.358 ± 0.071 TAE/g

in plant leaves. The lowest concentration of tannin is obtained in D.W. extract is 0.262 ± 0.009 TAE/g in plant leaves.

Table 3: Total Tannin content of plant sample

Plant parts	Concentrations ml	Total Tannin content of extract		
		Methanol	D.W.	Hexane
Leaves	1 ml	3.358 ± 0.071	0.262 ± 0.009	2.520 ± 0.001
Stem	1 ml	2.734 ± 0.213	-0.043 ± 0.0032	2.278 ± 0.002

3.2.3 Total flavonoids content:

The maximum concentration of total flavonoid content is obtained in methanolic extract of leaves

with value of 6.919 ± 0.055 QE/g. The lowest concentration of tannin in D.W. extract of leaves with value of 1.566 ± 0.006 QE/g.

Table 4: Total flavonoid content of plant sample

Plant parts	Concentration ml	Total Flavonoids content of extract		
		methanol	D.W.	Hexane

Leaves	1 ml	6.919±0.055	1.566±0.006	4.044±0.010
Stems	1 ml	0.860±0.003	1.118±0.001	7.056±0.003

3.3 Antioxidant activity:

3.3.1: DPPH ASSAY:

Graph 1: standard graph for DPPH assay

Graph 2: IC50 value of leaves and stem

The highest IC50 value is 20.728, present in the hexane extract of leaves. Lowest IC50 value is 5.204, present in methanolic leaves extract. The highest IC50 value present in hexane stem extract is 15.421 while

the lowest IC50 is present in methanol stem extract is 8.129.

3.3.2 PMA ASSAY:

Graph 3: Total PMA of plant sample

The highest PMA value is present in D.W. extract of leaves is 1.001 AAE/g. In the methanol leaves shows the the lowest value of PMA is 0.666 AAE/g. In the D.W extract of leaves contain a highest value of PMA

is 0.91 AAE/g, while the methanol stem extract contains a lowest value of PMA is 0.661 AAE/g.

3.4: Antibacterial activity:

Table: 5: Result of antimicrobial activity of Pennisetum setaceum (Forssk.) Chiov. plant

Plant parts	solvent	Zone of inhibition with bacterial strain in (mm)	
		Staphylococcus aureus	E. Coli
leaves	methanol	-	14 mm
	Acetone	-	-
	D.W.	-	-
Stems	Methanol	16 mm	-
	Acetone	20 mm	10 mm
	D.W.	-	-

The methanol and acetone extracts of stems show the zone of inhibition is 16 mm and 20 mm against E. coli bacteria. And the methanol extract of leaves shows a

14 mm of zone inhibition. And the acetone extract of stem shows 10 mm of zone inhibition.

Fig: 2: Antibacterial activity in stem Methanolic and acetone extract

Fig. 3: Antibacterial activity in leaf methanol and acetone

Fig. 4: Antibacterial activity in stem acetone

CONCLUSION:

The present study shows that the leaf and stem extracts of *Pennisetum setaceum* (Forssk.) Chiov. contain a large number of phytochemicals and antioxidant agents, which are useful in the drugs and medicines development. Additionally, a strong correlation was found between the antioxidant capacities of the plant and its TPC, TTC, TFC, PMA, and DPPH activity. This plant also exhibits a variety of phytochemicals studies in mostly major activity shown against the microorganisms. The antibacterial activity examined against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *E. coli* bacteria. The highest inhibition zone showed in acetone extract of stem, which is 20 mm.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

I am very thankful to Department of Botany, Gujarat University, for the providing instrument facilities and support. I am also grateful to Prof. Nainesh R. Modi and Prof. Dweipayan Goswami for providing guidance throughout this research work. I am also thankful to Mr. Milan Dabhi for the guidance and

support to perform antibacterial activity. I want to give gratitude to my mentor Miss. Riya for giving me constant guidance for this work

REFERENCE

1. Bagchi, K., & Puri, S. (1998). Free radicals and antioxidants in health and disease.
2. Biswas, B., Rogers, K., McLaughlin, F., Daniels, D., & Yadav, A. (2013). Antimicrobial activities of leaf extracts of guava (*Psidium guajava* L.) on two gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria. *International journal of microbiology*, 2013(1), 746165.
3. Gameti, J., Kumarkhaniya, H., Maitreya, B., Pandya, H., & Mankad, A. (2023). Phytochemical Analysis, Antioxidant Activity and Anti-Bacterial Activity of *Lysimachia Arvensis* Var. *Caerulea* L.
4. Gibson, E. L., Wardle, J., & Watts, C. J. (1998). Fruit and vegetable consumption, nutritional knowledge and beliefs in mothers and children. *Appetite*, 31(2), 205-228.
5. González-Rodríguez, A. M., Baruch, Z., Palomo, D., Cruz-Trujillo, G., Jiménez, M. S., & Morales,

- D. (2010). Ecophysiology of the invader *Pennisetum setaceum* and three native grasses in the Canary Islands. *Acta Oecologica*, 36(2), 248-254.
6. Harborne, J. B. (1984). Methods of plant analysis. In *Phytochemical methods: a guide to modern techniques of plant analysis* (pp. 1-36). Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands.
 7. Hasler, C. M., & Blumberg, J. B. (1999). Introduction 1. *The Journal of nutrition*, 129(3), 756S-757S.
 8. Huang, Z., Pan, X., Zhou, J., Leung, W. T., Li, C., & Wang, L. (2019). Chinese herbal medicine for acute upper respiratory tract infections and reproductive safety: a systematic review. *BioScience Trends*, 13(2), 117-129.
 9. Lahare, R. P., Yadav, H. S., Bisen, Y. K., & Dashahre, A. K. (2021). Estimation of total phenol, flavonoid, tannin and alkaloid content in different extracts of *Catharanthus roseus* from Durg district, Chhattisgarh, India. *Scholars Bulletin*, 7(1), 1-6.
 10. Lü, J. M., Lin, P. H., Yao, Q., & Chen, C. (2010). Chemical and molecular mechanisms of antioxidants: experimental approaches and model systems. *Journal of cellular and molecular medicine*, 14(4), 840-860.
 11. Mankad, A., Solanki, B., KumarKhaniya, H., & Maitreya, B. (2021). Phytochemical Analysis And Antioxidant Activities Of *Senna occidentalis* (L.) Leaves. *Towards Excellence*, 13(4).
 12. Mathai, K. (2000). Nutrition in the adult years. *Krause's food, nutrition, and diet therapy*, 10th ed., ed. LK Mahan and S. Escott-Stump, 271, 274-275.
 13. Pattni, R., Kumarkhaniya, H., Maitreya, B., & Modi, N. (2023). Phytochemical Analysis, Anti-Oxidant Activity and Anti-Bacterial Activity of *Salvadora Oleoides* L. *International Association Of Biologicals And Computational Digest*, 2(1), 183-190.
 14. Prakash, D., & Kumar, N. (2011). Cost effective natural antioxidants. *Nutrients, Dietary Supplements, and Nutraceuticals: Cost Analysis Versus Clinical Benefits*, 163-187.
 15. Samatha, T., Shyamsundarachary, R., Srinivas, P., & Swamy, N. R. (2012). Quantification of total phenolic and total flavonoid contents in extracts of *Oroxylum indicum* L. Kurz. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res*, 5(4), 177-179.
 16. Somawathi, K. M., Rizliya, V., Wijesinghe, D. G. N. G., & Madhujith, W. M. T. (2015). Antioxidant activity and total phenolic content of different skin coloured brinjal (*Solanum melongena*). *Tropical Agricultural Research*, 26(1).
 17. Williams, D. G., & Black, R. A. (1996). Effects of nutrient amendment and environment on growth and gas exchange for introduced *Pennisetum setaceum* in Hawaii. *Canadian Journal of Botany*, 74(2), 268-275.
 18. Yue, Y., Fan, X., Hu, Y., Han, C., Li, H., Teng, W., ... & Wu, J. (2020). In vitro induction and characterization of hexaploid *Pennisetum advena*, an ornamental grass. *Plant Cell, Tissue and Organ Culture (PCTOC)*, 142, 221-228.
 19. Zhishen, J., Mengcheng, T., & Jianming, W. (1999). The determination of flavonoid contents in mulberry and their scavenging effects on superoxide radicals. *Food chemistry*, 64(4), 555-559.
 20. Shaikh, J. R., & Patil, M. (2020). Qualitative tests for preliminary phytochemical screening: An overview. *International journal of chemical studies*, 8(2), 603-608.

HOW TO CITE: Kinjal Damor, Riya Kadia, Nainesh Modi*, Milan Dabhi, Dweipayan Goswami, Evaluation Of Phytochemicals, Antioxidant Potential, And Antibacterial Properties of Plant: *Pennisetum Setaceum* (Forssk.) Chiov, Int. J. Sci. R. Tech., 2025, 2 (4), 606-614. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15289389>